

Water-tightness Airborne Detection Implementation

D7.3. Report on the economic benefits for WADI demonstration sites ecosystems

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Executive Summary

In this D7.3, developed in the framework of the task 7.2, the economic benefits associated to WADI service based on the water provisioning services for the two demo areas (Monte Novo in Alqueva (Portugal) and Cabardèle, Vauvenarges and Verdagne in Provence (France)) involved in the project have been evaluated by means of CICES methodology.

First, the kind of environment present in the area was identified as the type of provisioning indicators related to water according to CICES. Second, questionnaires were sent to SCP and EDIA in order to collect the required information for calculating the indicators. Third, information gaps were covered by means of literature data and finally, CICES indicators were translated into economic impact in the area and for SCP and EDIA.

Once initial economic evaluation were performed based on water ecosystem provisioning services in both demo areas, and based on the assumption that a 5% of the total transported water is leaked and identified by means of WADI services (and leaks are repaired so water is not lost), the economic impact in both area were also estimated considering positive and detrimental effects related to the existence of water leaks.

In the case of Provence, three kinds of environment systems are found in the area: Forest, Croplands and Freshwater. For these environment systems, the total amount of water delivered by SCP is around 9,280,000 m³/y for irrigation, livestock and industrial exploitations, forest maintenance and urban with an economic impact in the area, related to water provision, of 93.92 M€/y (47 M€/y directly related to SCP service). The application of WADI service could lead to a water saving of up to 464,000 m³/y with a direct impact in SCP results of 165,000 €/y and CO₂ emissions reduction of 32 t/y only based on chemical dosage reduction and pumping.

In the case of Alqueva, only Croplands and a small part of freshwater environment system were found. For these environment systems, the total amount of water delivered by EDIA is around 27,200,000 m³/y for irrigation, livestock exploitations and urban with an economic impact in the area, related to water provision, of 31.66 M€/y directly related to EDIA service. The application of WADI service could lead to a water saving of up to 1,350,000 m³/y with a direct impact in EDIA results of 72,660 €/y and CO₂ emissions reduction of 155,4 t/y only based on a reduction in pumping.

Table of Content

1	Introduction	6
1.1	CICES methodology in a sight	6
2	Assessing the Ecosystem services for environmental benefits evaluation.....	8
2.1	CICES methodology applied to WADI project.....	8
3	Provence environmental evaluation.....	10
3.1	Goal scope.....	10
3.2	Cabardèle description.....	11
3.3	Vauvenargues description.....	12
3.4	Verdagne domain description.....	13
3.5	Description of CICES applicable indicators	14
3.6	Provisioning services indicators evaluation	16
3.7	Economic benefits in the ecosystem after applying the WADI service	20
4	Alqueva environmental evaluation	23
4.1	Alqueva description.....	23
4.2	Monte Novo description	23
4.3	Provisioning services indicators evaluation	25
4.3.1	Cultivated crops.....	26
4.3.2	Livestock resources	34
4.3.3	Water consumption	38
4.4	Economic benefits in the ecosystem after applying the WADI service	39
5	Conclusions.....	42
6	References.....	43
7	Anexes	47
7.1	Correspondences between CICES v4.3 classes the typologies of the MA and TEEB	47
7.2	Indicators for provisioning, regulating and cultural services for each kind of ecosystem....	48
7.3	Literature information extracted for irrigation water use evaluation	61
7.3.1	Assumptions.....	61
7.3.2	EDIA report information.....	62
7.3.3	Number of bovine heads by race and gender in Alentejo (2017).	64

1 Introduction

Defining a correct categorisation and description of ecosystem services (ES) is the basis of any attempt to perform an ecosystem assessment. It is also the correct way, in terms of transparency, to communicate findings to others in a standardized manner. This requires harmonisation for the different components of the assessment process, including definitions, classifications, and methods.

Different typologies of classifying ecosystem services have been defined along the time. Some examples are Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA) [1] or the Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB) [2] [3]. It is also possible to find more recent examples such as the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) [4] [5], an EU consultative document, the Nature's Contributions to People (NCP) [6] or the National Ecosystem Services Classification System (NESCS) [7] developed in the USA for measuring the human welfare impacts of policy-induced changes to ecosystems. At the end of the day, the previous classifications should be aim to be universal, but final researchers trends to avoid services thought to be relevant or custom the underlying definitions [8].

Due to the complexity of assessing the ES, and the lack of a single classification method, the comparisons and overviews are difficult so, additional effort in reconciling classification systems are necessary in a future for an efficient transition of concepts into management and policy decisions [8] [9].

In this DLV 7.3, the CICES v4.3 methodology has been applied in order to assess the current ecosystem services for both demo sites, Monte Novo (Alqueva, Portugal) and Provence, France. The selection of CICES methodology is based in two relevant concepts: it has been developed in the framework of a consultancy process in the EU, and it offers a high level of detail in a nested hierarchical structure of 'taxonomical levels' that was suitable for the chosen demo sites.

1.1 CICES methodology in a sight

The CICES methodology, created by means of an on-line consultative process, was developed based on the System of Environmental and Economic Accounting (SEEA) led by the United Nations Statistical Division (UNSD). Since its release, it has been commonly used in ES research for identifying and communicating specific services, and for ES mapping, assessment and valuation studies. The V4.3 of CICES used in the project was published at 2013 and it has been revised over an on-going work on an updated version (V5) that can be consulted in the CICES web site (www.cices.eu).

The initial idea behind the CICES methodology was to improve the MEA methodology with a special focus on creating a rigorous structure for classification. In common word, it was a manner to improve the distinction between services and benefits. Thus, in CICES, three different kind of services were create: provisioning, regulating and cultural.

Provisioning services are the material and energetic outputs from ecosystems from which goods and products are derived. The regulating services includes all the ways in which ecosystems can mediate the environment in which people live and benefit from them in terms of, for example, their health or security. Finally, cultural services identified all the non-

material characteristics of ecosystems that contribute to, or are important for people's mental or intellectual wellbeing.

CICES also took account of the fact that people uses to work at different scales, both geographically and thematically. It therefore used a structure with different sections that successively split the three major categories ('Sections') of provisioning, regulating and cultural into more detailed 'divisions', 'groups' and 'classes'. With this kind of structure, it was intended that users could go down to level of detail that they require, but then group or combine results when making comparisons or more generalised reports ('thematic scalability'). An example can be seen in the Figure 1, where a part of the provisioning hierarchical structure is shown.

Figure 1: Hierarchical structure for provisioning services [10].

As per Figure 1, we can see that below the class level no further hierarchical divisions were specified. Instead, the intention was that users could place the specific services that they were assessing in into one of the existing classes as 'class types'. Each class type should have an indicator. According to this, class definitions do not depend on any metric for services but rather description of ecosystem properties. All the classes and a comparison between CICES classes, and MA and TEEB classes can be found in annex 1 in the Table 24.

2 Assessing the Ecosystem services for environmental benefits evaluation

According to the MAES methodology [11], every class should be characterized by means of a measurable indicator. One of the interesting thing of this methodology is that indicators will depend on the kind of ecosystem and the availability of the data.

Four different kind of ecosystems can be found according to MAES [11]: forests, agro-ecosystems (cropland and grassland), freshwater ecosystems (rivers, lakes, groundwater and wetlands) and marine ecosystems (Marine inlets and transitional waters, coastal zones, shelf ecosystems and open ocean). For each ecosystem a set of indicators have been defined. These indicators can be found at Annex 2 in the tables 3 to 12.

A logical evaluation process for the ecosystem services could be defined as following: 1) to define the kind of ecosystem(s) present in the location/area to be studied, 2) to check the kind of section to be evaluated (provisioning, regulation and maintenance and/or cultural), 3) to evaluate the indicators that will be interesting or could be able to obtain data to calculate them. Once this process is complete, different alternatives rise in order to make use of the previous analysis. Some examples of the alternatives could be:

- To compare between different locations. This would be useful when similar ecosystems and indicators are used
- To gather all the indicators in a single value indicator (e.g. converting the indicators into economic impact), in order to classify/rate the ecosystem.
- To check alternative scenarios where environmental conditions will change. It would be possible by means of estimations or models to assess the impact in the indicator's values and then to evaluate possible impacts if these conditions are met. A simple example could be to evaluate the effect of building a dam in a river.

2.1 CICES methodology applied to WADI project

Two demo sites were chosen for testing the WADI service: the Provence region, in France, and the Alqueva region, in Portugal. The purpose for both sites are to transfer water in rural and suburban areas, being enough large to contain three kind of ecosystems within their boundaries: forest, croplands and freshwater.

Due to the large size of Provence, SCP choose three sub-areas to be studied (Le Tholonet, Vauvenargues and Cabardèle). In the case of Alqueva, EDIA suggested to study the MonteNovo sub-region.

The methodology process applied followed the previous evaluation process. In a first step the kind of ecosystems embed in the boundaries of the areas to be studied were identified. According to the kind of ecosystem, the provisioning indicators that could be representative for the area and that could be calculated. Then SCP, EDIA, official registered data and official reports were used in order to obtain the value for the indicators.

Because of the final aim of the task was to evaluate the economic effect in the ecosystem because of the application of the WADI service, in order to set the initial value for the economic effect the indicators were translated into economic terms.

After the translation into economic terms, it was possible to provide an estimation for the economic impact in the demo sites due to the direct use of water. The next logical step is to assess the effects on the indicators (or new ones that become relevant) after applying the WADI service. This methodology has a large assessing potential when it is applied to foresee the effects provoked by big changes (e.g. building a dam in a river, modifying the type of irrigation/source of water in order to change the crops or dredging a natural water channel). Both demo sites will be evaluated under this approach in order to check whether a transcendent impact takes places because the application of WADI service.

3 Provence environmental evaluation

3.1 Goal scope

Provence-Alps-Côte d'Azur (PACA in French) is one of the 13 regions of the metropolitan France (Figure 2), located in the south-east of the country. It has a surface of 31,400 km² and is divided in six Departments: High-Alps, Maritime Alps, High Provence Alps, Var, Vaucluse and Bouches du Rhone, as it can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 2 Interactive map of Metropolitan French Regions

WADI has three study areas in this Region: Cabardèle, Vauvenargues and Verdagne Domain. Two of them (Cabardèle and Vauvenargues) are located in Bouches du Rhone and the other one (Verdagne domain) in Var.

Figure 3 Departments of Provence

PACA's freshwater water is classified in the best water quality category [12]. Due to this reason, treatments for human consumption are simple, consisting in filtration and disinfection.

By the other hand, PACA's saltwater is composed by a part of the Mediterranean Sea called "The Blue Coast" (Eastside of Marseille, main city of PACA) and by an other part of the Mediterranean Sea called "Côte d'Azur". It has passed through some environmental problems, being its state very worrying during the 70s. However, Blue Coast's healthy is improving nowadays, in fact, it has been the object of different restoration programs directed by the Rhone/Mediterranean/Corse Water Agency. The most important one is called "Sauvons l'eau" (let's save the water) and it is an annual program who has different lines of action, such as rainwater management, pollutants treatment or climate change impacts on Sea [13].

3.2 Cabardèle description

As described before, Cabardèle is located in Bouches du Rhone Department, more specifically, it is mainly situated in the municipality of Lançon, though it also occupies part of the municipalities of Pélissanne and La Barben. Lançon has a population of 8,738 inhabitants and a surface of 69.7 Km². Pélissanne and La Barben have populations of 9,909 and 13,009 inhabitants and surfaces of 19.4 and 22.3 km², respectively. For its part, Cabardèle has a surface of 60.75 km², from which 48.1 have been studied by us.

Figure 4 Municipalities of Cabardèle

Figure 5 Cabardèle satellite image

Figure 6 Cabardèle Location

The studied area has different types of soil uses: urban, forest and croplands. The croplands in Lançon are mainly composed by vineyards, grapes, cereals, legumes, melons, tubercles and aromatic plants. At the same time, the principal bred animal species are sheeps, goats, horses and chickens.

In the north-east of the studied area there is an airport, which will not be included in the environmental assessment, due to the impossibility of flying above it.

Regarding to water uses, in 2018, Lançon consumed 610,524 m³ of irrigation water, 32,275 m³ of industrial water, 3,005 m³ of forest water (fire protection) and 613,200 m³ of domestic water.

3.3 Vauvenargues description.

Vauvenargues is the second area located in Bouches du Rhone department. In this case, the studied area is found between two different municipalities: Vauvenargues and Saint-Marc-Jaumegarde. The first one has a population of 1,032 inhabitants and a surface of 55.4 Km², while Saint-Marc-Jaumegarde counts with 1,193 inhabitants and 23.2 Km². If both are considered, they have a total surface of 78.6 km², from which our studied area comprises 51.75 Km².

Figure 7 Municipalities of Vauvenargues

Figure 8 Vauvenargues Satellite Image

Figure 9 Location of Vauvenargues

As Cabardèle, Vauvenargues has also different types of soil uses: forest (the principal one), croplands and urban. The main croplands are vineyards, cereals and aromatic plants, and the main bred species sheep, goat and horse.

The uses of water in Vauvenargues in 2,017 (in m³) are described in Table 1:

Table 1 Water uses in Vauvenargues.

Municipality	Irrigation	Industrial	Forest	Domestic
St-Marc-Jaumegarde	75,512	0	0	9,855 m ³ /year
Vauvenargues	221,361	0	0	43,800 m ³ /year

3.4 Verdagne domain description.

The third area, Verdagne domain, is situated in the Department of Var, among four different municipalities: St-Maximin/la Sainte Baume, Ollières, Seillons-Source d’Argens and Brue-Auriac.

St-Maximin is the biggest village of the zone, with a population of 15,753 inhabitants and a surface of 65 km². Furthermore, Ollières, Seillons-Source and Brue-Auriac have populations of 617, 2,525 and 1,289 and surfaces of 39.3, 25.6 and 37 km², respectively. All the municipalities have a total of 166.9 km², from which Verdagne domain comprises 99.5 km².

Figure 10 Municipalities of Verdagne Domain

Figure 11 Verdagne Domain Southern Satellite Image

Figure 12 Verdagne Domain Northern Satellite Image

Figure 13 Location of Verdagne Domain

The uses of the soil are again urban, forest and croplands, being the forest the most common one. The main types of croplands are vineyards (the main one), grapes, legumes, melons, tubercles and aromatic plants, and the principal breed species sheep, goats and chickens. Uses of water in 2017 (in m³) are described in Table 2.

Table 2 Water uses in Verdagne Domain

	Irrigation	Industrial	Forest	Domestic
St-Maximin	197,884	526	0	903,375 m ³ /year
Seillons-Source	59,170	14	0	109,500 m ³ /year
Brue-Auriac	388,173	27	0	88,695 m ³ /year

3.5 Description of CICES applicable indicators

As the three studied areas have a very similar economic activity, the indicators will be the same in the three cases, but the ones relative to “Freshwater indicators”, will be only applicable in those zones which have presence of lakes or rivers on them.

3.5.1.1 Forest indicators

Applicable forest indicators are showed in Table 3.

Table 3 List of applicable Forest indicators

Division	Group	Class	Indicator
Nutrition	Biomass	Wild plants, algae and their outputs	Honey production/consumption
		Wild animals and their outputs	Amount of meat (hunting)
	Water	Surface water for drinking	Area of forest dedicated to preserve the water resource Reservoir water
Materials	Biomass	Fibres and other materials from plants, algae and animals for direct use or processing	Forest biomass stock Forest for timber, pulp wood, etc. production.
Energy	Biomass-based energy sources	Plant-based resources	Fuel wood consumption

3.5.1.2 Agro-ecosystem indicators

Table 4 List of Applicable Agro-ecosystems indicators

Division	Group	Class	Cropland	Grassland
Nutrition	Biomass	Cultivated crops	Food and feed crop area (ha)	Grassland area (ha)
		Reared animals and their outputs	Livestock data (LU/ha, Ton/yr/region)	
	Water	Surface water for drinking	High Nature Value farmland	
		Ground water for drinking	Areas important for groundwater abstraction in agro-ecosystems	
Materials	Biomass	Fibres and other materials from plants, algae and animals for direct use or processing	Yields of fibre crops. Fibre crop area Manure	Not defined
		Materials from plants, algae and animals for agricultural use		
	Water	Surface water for non-drinking purposes	See freshwater ecosystems	
		Ground water for non-drinking purposes		
Energy	Biomass-based energy sources	Plant-based resources	Yields of energy crops Energy crop area Biofuel, biodiesel bioethanol (kToe)	Yields of grasslands for energy production (ton/ha, yon dry matter/ha, MJ/ha) Grassland for energy area (ha)

3.5.1.3 Freshwater indicators

Freshwater indicators are shown in the next table. "Surface water for drinking" indicators are only applicable in Vauvenargues and Verdagne Domain, as there are neither lakes nor rivers in Cabardèle.

Table 5 List of applicable Freshwater Indicators

Division	Group	Class	Lakes	Rivers	Ground water	Wetlands
Materials	Water	Surface water for drinking	Water exploitation index (WEI)	Water use per sector Surface water availability Water abstracted Volume of water bodies	Not defined	Surface of flood-prone areas
		Ground water for drinking		Not defined	Ground water bodies Ground water abstraction	Not defined

3.6 Provisioning services indicators evaluation

In order to obtain the information about the ecosystem services in Provence, literature was searched. Among others, the most important resource found was a SIG elaborated by the Regional Observatory of Water and Aquatic Ecosystems from PACA (Observatoire Régional de l'Eau et des Milieux Aquatiques, in French), from which a lot of information about soil uses, types of crops and forest lands was found. Some other sources were found, such as a Report of the Regional Department of Feeding, Agriculture and Forest from PACA or some academic articles.

In addition, the water uses information was asked to SCP.

3.6.1.1 Cultivated crops

As described before, information about types of crops was found in the SIG [14] and is showed in

Table 6:

Table 6 Surfaces of cultivated crops

Surface by type of crop (Ha)	Cabardèle	Vauvenargues	Verdagne Domain
Grassland	87.24	99.89	223.35
Vineyards	459.59	16.24	1247.48
Greenhouses	8.41	0	2.71
Arboriculture	153.58	11.46	8.56
Olive trees	52.18	2.2	12.02
Total	761	129.79	1504.12

Table 7 Environmental impact associated to water by kind of crop

		TOTAL	Grassland	Vineyards	Green house	Arboriculture	Olive trees
Cabardèle	Irrigated area [Ha]	761	87.24	459.59	8.41	153.58	52.18
	Water consumption [m ³ /y]	3,143,273	668,781	1,263,872	55,808	998,270	156,540
	Production [Ton/y]	8,671	1,413	4,021	329	2,411	495
	Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	4,473,113	91,944	2,139,391	62,838	2,019,137	159,801
	Economic impact on area [k€/y]	14,226,888	250,721	8,320,877	106,528	5,130,668	418,092
Vauvenargues	Irrigated area [Ha]	129.79	99.89	16.24	0	11.46	2.2
	Water consumption [m ³ /y]	765,750	44,660	0	74,490	6,600	891,506
	Production [Ton/y]	1,618	142.1	0	179.9	20.9	1,961.1
	Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	338,277	105,277	75,597	0	150,666	6,737
	Economic impact on area [k€/y]	981,575	287,077	294,025	0	382,846	17,628
Verdagne D.	Av. Irrigated area [Ha]	1,504	223.35	1,247.48	2.71	8.56	12.02
	Av. Water consumption [m ³ /y]	3,567,753	1,712,201	3,458,070	17,983	55,640	36,060
	Av. Production [Ton/y]	11,357	3,618.27	11,002.95	106.23	134.39	114.19
	Av. Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	6,230,052	235,395	5,853,569	20,248	112,539	8,299
	Av. Economic impact on area [k€/y]	23,796,658	641,892	22,766,675	34,327	284,965	67,798

To obtain the water consumption and the economic impact of the crops, the same methodology than in the case of Monte Novo was used, and results are presented in

Table 7 .

The total surfaces of the three studied areas have been considered. Moreover, water consumptions have been calculated from the consumption data of Portugal's crops. The overall amount of water considered for irrigation is **7,476,776 m³/y** (42% Cabardèle, 10.25% Vauvenargues and 47.75% Verdagne). Regarding the use, 32.4% corresponds to animal use (grassland for feeding) and 67.6% to human feeding (15.4% olive trees, 15.1% Arboriculture, 2.1% greenhouse and 67.3% vineyards). The associated economic impact in the area corresponds to approximately **39M€/y** (36.5% Cabardèle, 2.5% Vauvenargues and 61% Verdagne). Regarding the use, 3% corresponds to animal use (grassland for feeding) and 97% to human feeding (80.5% vineyards, 0.4% greenhouse, 14.9% arboriculture and 4.2% olive trees).

3.6.1.2 Livestock resources

With the aim of finding data about the animal production and its economic impact, literature was searched. The number of animals by Provence Departments was found in a report elaborated by the Regional Department of Feeding, Agriculture and Forest [15], as it can be seen in Table 8:

Table 8 Number of bred animals per Department

	Ovine	Bovine	Caprine	Hives
Bouches du Rhône (Cabardèle and Vauvenargues)	220,187	19,239	5,367	14,200
Var (verdagne)	57,693	1,077	4,198	24,600

according to it [15], the economic impact of animal breeding in Bouches du Rhône supposes, approximately 13 million euros, and 11 million euros for Var. No detailed data was found in official and open reports so, in order to find the economic impact in the three demo areas, the overall economic impact for the departments was estimated according to the demo surfaces (extrapolation). That would suppose an approximated economic impact of **725,000 euros in both Cabardèle and Vauvenargues**. At the same time the approximated impact in **Verdagne Domain** will be **1.38 M€**. SCP was consulted about the amount of water delivered by this uses. According to SCP data, they are not providing water for all the industrial and livestock exploitation but a small part. The total amount delivered by SCP in the three areas cannot distinguish between industrial and livestock exploitation (because they are registering both consumptions together). This amount of water is shared approximately in this manner 32,840 m³/y water (22.1% Vauvenargues, 32.1% Cabardèle and 45.8% Verdagne Domain). It is not possible to distinguish between Ovine, Bovine Caprine and Hives. Based on SCP information, the price for water, for livestock purposes is set to 0.39148 €/m³ plus a fix tariff per exploitation and water capacity. It is not possible to know the number of exploitations but, based on the amount of water, at least the incomes from livestock exploitations should be 12.856 €/y.

3.6.1.3 Forest resources

In the same way as in the case of the livestock resources, a study about the forest economic impact in Provence was found. It described [16] the economic impact of the "Mediterranean forest", a concept that involves the surfaces of Provence, Corse,

Languedoc, la Drôme, and l'Ardèche. From this point, the economic impact of the forest in the three study cases was calculated, as shown in Table 9:

Table 9 Economic impact of forest

	Surface (Ha)	Forest (k€)	Flora (k€)	Hunting (k€)
PACA	31,400	-	-	-
Corse	8,680	-	-	-
Languedoc	22,209	-	-	-
La Drôme	6,530	-	-	-
L'Ardèche	5,529	-	-	-
Total M. Forest	74,348	1.79·10 ⁴	2.34·10 ⁴	5.8·10 ³
Cabardèle	60.75	14.6	19.1	4.74
Vauvenargues	51.75	12.5	16.3	4.04
Verdagne Domain	99.5	24	31.3	7.76

Regarding water consumption, SCP provided water provided for forest maintenance. Neither Cabardèle, not Vauvenargues are provided by SCP. Verdagne consumes 3,005 m³/y. According to SCP the incomes from this water is close to 2,905 €/y.

3.6.1.4 Water consumption for household purposes

Water consumption and economic impact of the three areas has been calculated from the data contributed by SCP for household purposes. This information is included in Table 10.

Table 10 Water consumption in Provence Study Cases for domestic purposes

	Water consumption (m ³ /y)	Economic Impact (€/y)
Cabardèle	1,101,571	3,098,100
Vauvenargues	53,655	150,730
Verdagne Domain	613,200	1,724,660
TOTAL	1,768,426	4,973,490 €

Regarding water consumption, we can see an accumulated annual consumption of 1,768,426 m³/y (62.3% Cabardèle, 3.0% Vauvenargues and 34.7% Verdagne). Regarding the price for household water, the average house will pay 368€/y (fix tariff) plus 1.17€/m³ up to 250 m³/y and then 0.58€/m³. SCP cannot provide the number of households provided neither the number of inhabitants per home. Based on the same approach than in the case of Alqueva, Portugal, 164l/person/day is assumed with an average of 3.74 persons/house, it can be assumed the number of house for each demo site, resulting in an average consumption of 224 m³/y-house.

Summing up, based on the previous information we can summarize the water consumption and the economic impact associated to its use in the Table 11.

Table 11: Water consumption and economic impact for SCP water supply in Provence.

		Cabardèle	Vauvenargues	Verdagne
Water consumption (€/m³)	Crops irrigation	3,143,273	765,750	3,567,753
	Industrial + livestock	10,541.6	7,257.6	15,040.7
	Forest	0	0	3,005
	Domestic	1,101,571	53,655	613,200
	TOTAL	4,255,385	826,662	4,198,998
Economic impact (€/y)	Crops irrigation	14,226,888	981,575	23,796,658
	Industrial + livestock	729,126	732,257	1,385,888
	Forest	38,440	32,840	65,965
	Domestic	3,098,100	150,730	1,724,660
	TOTAL	18,092,514	1,987,402	26,973,171

3.7 Economic benefits in the ecosystem after applying the WADI service

The next and final step in the analysis is to quantify the economic benefits associated to the use of WADI service. Water leaks can be on one side environmentally profitable (i.e. providing wild flora and fauna water or recharging underground repositories). On the other side, saving water by water leaks detection and subsequent reparation will save electricity (pumping), chemicals (when water treatment is present) and will increase water availability (that could be useful for other purposes as additional irrigation, water transfers, etc.)

In the three demo areas in Provence we can find groundwater repositories, forest areas, wild flora/fauna, irrigation crops and human/industrial provision.

On the one hand, benefits related to water leaks should be assessed. Regarding to the nexus water-forest, there is not any doubt the symbiotic relation between them. Because of forests, water availability is multiplied, due to water retention (avoiding ground erosion

that will lead to an increase in the economic impact in the area up to a 51% [17]) and to an increase in the water rainfall. Additionally, higher water availability generates higher wild biodiversity. It is not easy to account for the economic impact related to water provisioning services in forest environments. According to [18], woodlands and grasslands forests (the ones present in Provence area) could represent an economic impact between 13 and 179 \$/ha/year respectively. Water leaks that could provide a greater amount of water to forests that could increase their surface would lead to indirect increase in the area's economic impact. Nevertheless, water transfer structures in Provence's area are not built under forests and only a small amount of water is dedicated to firefight purposes.

Another positive effect of water leaks when underground repositories are present (as it happens in all the Provence demo areas) is the free groundwater repositories recharge and an improvement in their water quality. Some studies dedicated to this effect [19] quantify it between 6 to 8.8 €/m³_{recharged}. It is not available information regarding the amount of water leaked that could be naturally derived into this effect, neither the amount of leaked water but, in all the three areas (602 ha in Cabardèle, 205 ha in Vauvenargues and 1035 ha in Verdagne) it is possible to find groundwater repositories [14], so this effect could be also beneficial.

On the other hand, water leaks represent negative impact on the environment and on the economic account of SCP, the company that should provide water to end-users. The indirect effects related can be identified based on the existence of water leaks: an increase in the total amount of energy for pumping water and an increase in the amount of chemicals used in water treatment plants for human water delivery.

For the first effect, SCP pumping consumption by kind of water use is not available. Chemical dosage is not also available. For pumping electricity consumption, a value of 0.5 kWh/m³ has been used (similar to Portuguese demo case). For chemical dosage, during demo visit, reverse osmosis was identified as water treatment technology. Antiscalant and softening regular treatments have been assumed with a cost between 0.1 and 0.28 €/m³ (for 100 ppm and 250 ppm output water) [20].

At this moment it is not known quantitatively the capacity of detecting amount of leaked water by means of WADI service. Due to this, and based on the DLV 9.1 assumptions, a 5% of the total water provided by SCP in the areas has been assumed as leaked and detected. Under this assumption, in the Table 12, for a electricity price between [21] (0.0974 – 0.1534 €/kWh without and with taxes), the economic impact of detecting water leaks only based on negative effects have been included.

Table 12: Water savings for SCP based on water leak detection capacity of WADI service.

	Cabardèle	Vauvenargues	Verdagne
Water consumption (m³/y)	4,255,385	826,662	4,198,998
Electricity consumption (kWh/y)	2,127,692	413,331	2,099,499
Chemical additives (€/y)	110,157 – 308,440	5,365 – 15,023	61,320 – 171,696
Potential water savings (m³/y)	212,769	41,333	209,950
Electricity reduction (kWh/y)	106,384	20,666	104,975
Chemical savings (€/y)	21,277 – 59,575	4,133 – 11,573	20,995 – 58,786
Economic savings for SCP (€/y)	31,639 – 75,894	6,146 – 14,743	31,220 – 74,890
Electrical CO₂ savings (kgCO₂/y) [22]	14,255	2,770	14,067

D7.3. Report on the economic benefits for WADI demonstration sites ecosystems.

Additionally, more water could be available for SCP to be provided (the saved one), so based on this, higher incomes could be reached by SCP in they could sell this water.

4 Alqueva environmental evaluation

4.1 Alqueva description

Alentejo is a Portugal's geographic region located in the mid-south. The Alqueva reservoir, located in the geographical region of Alentejo, is the largest artificial lake in Europe occupying an area of 250 km². This artificial lake, built by means of a Dam, can cover a water catchment area around 10,000 km² where 20 municipalities are provided with water (i.e. Beja, Évora, Setúbal and Portalegre).

One of the major challenges of the Alqueva Irrigation Scheme was to benefit with irrigation 110.000 ha of dryland area. The construction of the Alqueva Dam was part of the EFMA project (Alqueva Multi-purpose Undertaking) that comprised the following infrastructures [23]: 1) the Alqueva Dam (4150 hm³ of capacity), 2) the Alqueva Hydroelectric Power Station (520 MWe), 3) the Pedrógão Dam (106 hm³), 4) the Pedrógão mini Hydroelectric plant (10 MW) and the general irrigation system (120 km², 362 km of primary network, 1,620 km of secondary network, 47 pumping stations, 69 reservoirs). All these infrastructures can be seen in the Figure 14.

Figure 14: EFMA project infrastructures located in Alqueva's ecosystem [23].

4.2 Monte Novo description

This project located in the Alentejo Region has a huge potential because it is on a traditional agricultural area, which has favorable agro-weather conditions for irrigated crops. In the framework of this study, EDIA was consulted in order to select an interesting area to develop the WADI demo activities and the ecosystem assessment. The area chosen was the Monte Novo area. In the Figure 15, it is possible to see an aerial picture of the zone.

Figure 15: Monte Novo area [23].

The Monte Novo area is divided into 4 areas ("Bloco") according to the relative position to water reservoirs and 7 subareas. The water is taken from a water reservoir in the north and then is transferred by means of an artificial water channel through the territory. In every small water reservoir (corresponding to a "Bloco") a pumping station is located and then pressured and gravity irrigation systems are distributed from them.

According to EDIA clarifications, three water uses can be found in the Monte Novo region: crops irrigation, residential users and livestock farms. No forests are located in the area and as in-land site, no coastal or marine areas found. According to this description and aerial images, the ecosystem was classified as an agro-ecosystem and the provisioning indicators can be consulted in Table 28.

In order to obtain the economic benefit due to the water use, the indicators for each class were evaluated with EDIA in order to assess whether they were representative for the area under study.

According to EDIA, regarding the nutrition division it was possible in the ecosystem it was possible to find cultivated crops and reared animals but no wild plants, algae or animals in

aquaculture. In this division, for the water group surface water for drinking purposes is found (for animals and for human uses) but no groundwater exploitation.

Regarding the materials division, no plants, algae, animals or wild fauna/flora are used for fibers or materials for any productive process unless some medical crops. Regarding the non-drinking water as material, surface water it is found for irrigation but not for any industrial process. No groundwater is used.

In terms of Energy division, a small fraction energetic crop is available but no animal wastes are used for biogas or biofuels.

A reduced version of the Table 28 can be found in Table 13, with a list of the provisioning services that were considered representative for Monte Novo.

Table 13: Monte Novo representative provisioning ecosystem services indicators.

Division	Group	Class	Cropland
Nutrition	Biomass	Cultivated crops	Yield of food and feed crops (Ton/year) Food and feed crop area (ha)
		Reared animals and their outputs	Livestock data (Lu/ha)
	Water	Surface water for drinking	Water consumption for human and animal uses (mM ³ /year)
Materials	Biomass	Genetic materials from all biota	Yield of crops (Ton/year) Crop area (ha)
	Water	Surface water for non-drinking purposes	Water consumption for irrigation uses (mM ³ /year)
Energy	Biomass-based energy sources	Plant-based resources	Yield of energetic crops (Ton/year) Crop area (ha)

4.3 Provisioning services indicators evaluation

Considering the previous indicators, the next step in the evaluation were to obtain the value for each indicator based on the available data.

In order to obtain the yield of food and feed crops, the energetic crops and the medical crops for each area and sub-area, registered data where asked to EDIA. EDIA was able to provide for each area and sub-area maps where the crops per smallholding for 2017. In this sense, by means of the maps and the legend (see Figure 16) it was possible to obtain the kind of irrigation system, the water source and the crops (kind and surface). This information is found in Table 14. Once the crop surface per kind of crop was obtained, the annual average yield production per kind of crop was obtained from the annual agriculture 2017 report for the Alqueva area published by EDIA [24]. A summary of the used data from this report is available in the Table 35 in the Annex 3.

Figure 16: Crops per smallholding for Monte Novo in 2017.

Table 14: Crops, irrigation pressure and water source per smallholding for Monte Novo in 2017.

Sub-area	Pressure level	Water source	Crops
4.2	Low	Directly from Res 4.1	Sunflower, forage, olive tree intensive, tomatoes, garlic
4.1	High	Pumping from Res 4	Olive tree, forage, tomatoes, pepper
4.a	High	Pumping from Res 4.1	Gray grass, grapes for wine, olive tree, tomatoes, soft wheat, broccoli, forage, olive tree intensive, Corn
3	Low	Directly from Res 3	Forage, olive tree intensive, sunflower, Broccoli, olive tree, Corn
2	High	Pumping from Res 2	Forage, Corn, vegetable, garlic, Broccoli, grapes for wine, olive tree intensive, pumpkin, hard wheat, aromatic plants, fruit tree
1.2	High	Pumping from Res 1	Forage, tomatoes, grapes for wine, almond
1.1	High with a small area with low pressure	Directly from Res 1	Grapes for wine, almonds, corn, tomatoes, forage, sunflowers, olive tree intensive, broccoli, garlic, sorghum, Lucerne

For water consumption (drinking and non-drinking purposes) for irrigation, humans and livestock different sources were consulted. Specific irrigation consumptions by kind of crop were extracted from the EDIA's annual agriculture report [24]. Specific livestock water consumption was extracted from literature [25]. According to EDIA indications, only bovine farms could be found in the area. Regarding the human water consumption, three categories were considered in the urban cycle of water: water supply, water depuration and waste management. This information was provided by EDIA and ECODEPUR (the constructor company for the only wastewater treatment plant found in the area).

By following the extracted data is included by three different categories: cultivated crops, water consumption and livestock resources.

4.3.1 Cultivated crops

According to the graphical information provided by EDIA **5,141.9 ha of cultivated crops** with a distribution of **cereals (8.5%)**, **pasture (26.4%)**, **oleaginous (3.1%)**, **aromatic and medicinal (1.6%)**, **fruit (37.4%)**, **nut (4.7%)** and **horticultural (18.3%)** can be found in a perimeter of **7,700 ha**. The share based on the **usage** of the crops is distribution **64.1%** for **human feeding**, **34.1%** for **animal feeding**, **0.15%** for **energy uses** and **1.6%** for aromatic and **medicinal uses**.

As already described, the demo area is divided into 4 areas according to the relative position to water reservoirs and 7 subareas. By following a summary of ground usage, food and feed crops, yield, agriculture profits and economic impact for each the area is shown.

Area 1

When the water implications on the area and the relationship with the economic value for irrigation purposes are assessed, it is possible to confirm that, for the area 1, the **human feeding crops** mean the **62.7%** of **water consumption**, **animal feeding** the **35.0%**, **energy crops** the **0.1%** and aromatics and **medical crops** the **2.3%**.

Bearing in mind the **agricultural economic profits** there is not a linear relation, being the share **89.4%** the **human feeding crops** and **10.6%** **animal feeding crops**.

Regarding specific types of crops, in the Figure 17 we can see the water consumption share and the agricultural economic profit share. As a colour scheme, purple corresponds to Aromatics and Medical crops, orange to cereals, yellow to oleaginous, green to grass and forage, red to horticultural, blue to fruit trees and light brown to nuts.

Figure 17: Water consumption and Agricultural economic profits for area 1 by crop.

Table 15: Area 1 water consumption, yield and economic impact by crop use.

		TOTAL	Human feeding crops	Animal feeding crops	Energy crops	Aromatic and Medical crops
Subarea 1.1	Irrigated area [Ha]	1,475.5	979.4	416.4	3.1	76.6
	Water consumption [Mm ³ /y]	7,123.7 – 8,440.8	3,872.6 – 5,076.1	3,051.8 – 3,082.5	7.7 – 13.8	191.7 – 268.4
	Production [Ton/y]	31,433.4 – 35,176.3	26,482.6 – 29,747.2	4,821.1 – 5,263.4	7.7 – 12.3	115 – 153.4
	Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	5,483.7 – 5,910.3	4,799.5 – 5,082.4	680.7 – 823.9	3.5 – 3.9	N/A
	Economic impact on area [k€/y]	8,564.1 – 9,527	7,495.6 – 8,192.5	1,063.1 – 1,328.1	5.5 – 6.4	N/A
Subarea 1.2	Irrigated area [Ha]	326.6	265.4	61.2	0	0
	Water consumption [Mm ³ /y]	2,214.1 – 2,568.3	1,724.7 – 2,078.9	489.4	0	0
	Production [Ton/y]	6,615.7 – 7,706.3	6,003.9 – 6,972.2	611.8 – 734.1	0	0
	Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	2,052 – 2,416.5	1,984.7 – 2,315.5	67.3 – 100.9	0	0
	Economic impact on area [k€/y]	3,126.9 – 3,702.4	3,024.3 – 3,547.8	102.5 – 154.7	0	0
Area 1	Av. Irrigated area [Ha]	1,802.1	1,244.8	477.6	3.1	76.6
	Av. Water consumption [Mm ³ /y]	10,173.3	6,376.1	3,556.5	10.7	230
	Av. Production [Ton/y]	40,645.9	34,602.9	5,715.5	10	134.2
	Av. Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	7,920.4	7,080.3	836.4	3.7	N/A
	Av. Economic impact on area [k€/y]	12,016.9	11,130.1	880.9	5.9	N/A

In the Table 15, the detailed information is included. It should be highlighted the difference between agricultural economic profit and economic impact. The first one is considering only the cultivated field economic profits meanwhile the second term also account for the economic costs related to the farm exploitation.

Area 2

The water implications on the area 2 and its relationship with the economic value for irrigation purposes leads to the following results: the **human feeding crops** mean the **15.4%** of **water consumption**, **animal feeding** the **84.1%** and aromatics and **medical crops** the **0.5%**. Bearing in mind the **agricultural economic profits** there is not a linear relation, being the share **48,0%** the **human feeding crops** and **52,0%** animal **feeding crops**.

Regarding specific types of crops, in the Figure 18 we can see the water consumption share and the agricultural economic profit share.

Figure 18: Water consumption and Agricultural economic profits for area 2 by crop.

As a colour scheme, purple corresponds to Aromatics and Medical crops, orange to cereals, green to grass and forage, red to horticultural and blue to fruit trees.

In the Table 16, the detailed information is included.

Table 16: Area 2 water consumption, yield and economic impact by crop use.

		TOTAL	Human feeding crops	Animal feeding crops	Energy crops	Aromatic and Medical crops
Area 2	Av. Irrigated area [Ha]	763.6	204.4	550.5	0	8.8
	Av. Water consumption [Mm ³ /y]	5,155.7	793.8	4,335.8	0	26.3
	Av. Production [Ton/y]	9,705.2	3,431.9	6,255.4	0	15.4
	Av. Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	1,778.6	635.1	687.3	0	N/A
	Av. Economic impact on area [k€/y]	1,912.5	976.0	936.5	0	N/A

Area 3

The assessment of the water implications on the area 3 and the relationship with the economic value for irrigation purposes shows that the **human feeding crops** represent the **48.3%** of **water consumption**, the **animal feeding** a **51.4%** and **energy crops** a **0.3%**. Bearing in mind the **agricultural economic profits** there is not a linear relation, being the **share 85.8%** the **human feeding crops** and **14.1%** **animal feeding crops**.

In the Figure 19 we can see the water consumption share and the agricultural economic profit share by crop. As a colour scheme, orange corresponds to cereals, yellow to oleaginous, green to grass and forage, red to horticultural and blue to fruit trees.

Figure 19: Water consumption and Agricultural economic profits for area 3 by crop.

In the Table 17, the detailed information is included.

Table 17: Area 3 water consumption, yield and economic impact by crop use.

		TOTAL	Human feeding crops	Animal feeding crops	Energy crops	Aromatic and Medical crops
Area 3	Av. Irrigated area [Ha]	742	519	220.4	2.6	0
	Av. Water consumption [Mm ³ /y]	3,166.3	1,529.2	1,628.5	8.6	0
	Av. Production [Ton/y]	18,027.9	5,028.1	12,636.1	363.7	0
	Av. Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	2,638.8	2,263.2	372.4	3.2	0
	Av. Economic impact on area [k€/y]	3,623.4	3,107	512.1	4.3	0

Area 4

Whenever we analyze the water implications on the area and the relationship with the economic value for irrigation purposes, we can check that for the area 4 the **human feeding crops** mean the **54.6%** of **water consumption**, **animal feeding** the **45.2%** and **energy crops** the **0.1%**. Bearing in mind the **agricultural economic profits** there is not a linear relation, being the share **81.0%** the **human feeding crops** and **18.9%** **animal feeding** crops.

Figure 20: Water consumption and Agricultural economic profits for area 4 by crop.

Regarding specific types of crops, in the Figure 20 we can see the water consumption share and the agricultural economic profit share. As a colour scheme, orange to cereals, yellow to oleaginous, green to grass and forage, red to horticultural and blue to fruit trees.

In the Table 18, the detailed information is included.

Table 18: Area 4 water consumption, yield and economic impact by crop use.

		TOTAL	Human feeding crops	Animal feeding crops	Energy crops	Aromatic and Medical crops
Subarea 4.1	Irrigated area [Ha]	558.3	335.0	223.3	0	0
	Water consumption [Mm ³ /y]	4,082.6 – 4,592.4	2,296.1 – 2,805.9	1,786.5	0	0
	Production [Ton/y]	22,204.7 – 24,920.8	19,971.3 – 22,241	2,233.1 – 2,679.8	0	0
	Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	2,667.4 – 2,795.1	2,421.8 – 2,426.7	245.6 – 368.5	0	0
	Economic impact on area [k€/y]	4,766.6 – 5,215.5	4,327.6 – 4,528	439 – 687.5	0	0
Subarea 4.2	Irrigated area [Ha]	646.2	481.4	162.6	2.2	0
	Water consumption [Mm ³ /y]	3,063.4 – 3,640.1	2,282.3- 2,712.0	770.7 – 915.8	10.3 – 12.3	0
	Production [Ton/y]	10,524.9 – 12,092.4	7,841.3 – 9,009.1	2,648.1 – 3,042.5	35.5 – 40.8	0
	Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	2,739 – 3,018.6	2,040.7 – 2,248.9	689.1 – 759.5	9.2 – 10.2	0
	Economic impact on area [k€/y]	4,039 – 4,533.1	3,009.1 – 3,377.3	1,016.2 – 1,140.5	13.6 – 15.3	0
Subarea 4.a	Irrigated area [Ha]	629.1	509.7	119.3	0	0
	Water consumption [Mm ³ /y]	2,222.8 – 2,647.8	1,801.1 – 2,145.5	421.7 – 502.3	0	0
	Production [Ton/y]	6,906.9 – 7,866.7	5,595.8 – 6,374.3	1,310.1 – 1,492.4	0	0
	Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	2,149.6 – 2,253.2	1,741.8 -1,825.7	407.8 – 427.6	0	0
	Economic impact on area [k€/y]	2,919.4 – 3,182.3	2,365.5 – 2,578.5	553.8 – 603.7	0	0
Area 4	Av. Irrigated area [Ha]	1,833.6	1,326.2	505.2	2.2	0
	Av. Water consumption [Mm ³ /y]	10,124.5	7,021.4	3,091.7	11.3	0
	Av. Production [Ton/y]	42,258.2	35,516.4	6,703	38.2	0
	Av. Agricultural economic profit [k€/y]	7,811.5	6,352.8	1,399	9.7	0
	Av. Economic impact on area [k€/y]	12,328.0	10,093.1	2,220.4	14.5	0

In general terms, it is possible to evaluate the water consumption, the agricultural profit and the economic impact on the area based on the economic conversion of cultivated crops. The **overall water consumption** for **crops irrigation** rises up to **27,097 Mm³/y**. The **economic impact** in the area associated to this water consumption can be estimated in **29.88 M€ excluding** the aromatics and **medical crops** that are directly commercialized between final user companies and farmers.

In the following Figure 21 and Figure 22, a summary of the area by crops use and type is included:

Figure 21: Water use and economic impact for irrigation purposes for 2017 in Monte Novo.

Figure 22: Water consumption and agricultural economic profits by crop for 2017 in Monte Novo.

Some conclusions can be extracted from the water use for irrigation purposes and the economic impact on the ecosystem:

- In general terms it is possible to see that, regarding the water use, grass and forage cultivation represent almost half of the overall water consumption in the area, followed by olive tree, tomato and corn. When a translation into economic impact is done, the olive tree in the area is the main profitable crop, followed by tomato and forage and Walnut.

- Human feeding crops is paired in terms of water use to animal feeding crops, being energy and medical crops anecdotic. When this water use is translated into economic impact, human uses represent almost 85% meanwhile animal uses a 15%.
- In the Monte Novo area it is possible to find at the same time high water demand crops such as corn or sunflowers and water resistant crops such as olive trees or grapes. Additionally, it is possible to alternate high rain periods during winter with very dry periods during summer.

4.3.2 Livestock resources

In order to evaluate the livestock impact in the ecosystem (economic base) an initial contact with EDIA was performed to consult the number of farms/kind of livestock in the area under study. Unfortunately, the contacts with EDIA and a search for public repositories resulted in a lack of information for this requirement.

CIRCE contacted to CONFAGRI (Confederação Nacional de Cooperativas Agrícolas e do Crédito Agrícola de Portugal), and could obtain data for livestock registers but the maximum detail provided by the database was the overall area (Alentejo). In order to provide at least a qualitative data, based in the surface of the Region of Alentejo (Portugal), 27.292 km² and the area under study, 77 km², a lineal conversion by surface were done.

By following the number of heads by race in the Alentejo area related to the animal farms are presented.

Porcine:

According to the database of livestock management in the area of Alentejo, the porcine livestock can be classified according to 12 categories (weight fattening purpose based and male and female reproductive purposes based).

By following data for 2016 and 2017 Q1 are presented. In order to evaluate the 2017 complete period a trend analysis was done in order to complete the Q2 to Q4 data.

Table 19: Alentejo porcine heads livestock for 2016 and 2017.

	2016			2017
	April	August	December	April
Fattening				
< 20 Kg	315,959	317,091	285,525	299,879
> 110 kg	18,699	19,840	46,829	13,478
20 to 50 Kg	223,455	225,369	218,006	211,998
50 to 80 kg	187,411	189,430	174,174	157,009
80 to 110 kg	122,431	123,168	144,684	115,866
Sows				
2 nd or additional pregnancy sows	49.565	50.049	48.230	47.439
Lactating or waiting for mating sows	18.657	18.750	17.972	18.039
1 st pregnancy sows (already covered)	11.705	11.763	10.926	11.952
Waiting for 1 st pregnancy sows (not covered)	7.431	7.461	8.501	8.982

Boars				
Adult boars in breeding	1.966	2.004	1.640	1.708
Adult boars > 50kg not in breeding	258	260	225	225
Adult boars waiting for slaughter	1.420	1.429	1.382	1.173

According to conversation with EDIA, there are no porcine farms in the area under study.

Bovine:

According to the database of livestock management in the area of Alentejo, the bovine livestock can be classified by race, gender and age. The information obtained from databases is extracted for 2017 and can be found in the Annex 3 in Table 36.

After consulting EDIA, they confirmed that in the area under study some bovine exploitation farms can be found, but they cannot provide specific data for these facilities. By following in the Table 20, a lineal extrapolation by surface (77 km²), the preferable use by race according to literature (meat or milk) [26] and a classification by gender and age is included.

Some assumptions have been done:

- Cruzado has been considered 50/50 for milk and meat.
- Only milk races and female cows with more than 1 year have been considered for milk use
- 75% of male and female cows for meat races have been considered for meat use
- Milk races female cows with less than 1 year, 25% of male and female meat races and 100% male of milk races have been considered for breeding and growing
- The other uses have been assumed as the previous classification.

Table 20: Lineal extrapolation to Monte Novo for heads of bovine livestock by race, use, gender and age.

Race	Preferable use	Gender	Heads of livestock by age		
			<1 year	1-2 years	>2 years
ABERDEEN-ANGUS	Meat	F	1	1	3
		M	1	1	1
ALENTEJANA	Meat	F	9	8	70
		M	8	5	1
BARROSA	Meat	F	0	0	2
BLONDE D'AQUITAINE	Milk	F	0	0	1
BRAVA DE LIDE	Meat	M	5	5	12
		F	5	5	29
CACHENA	Meat	F	1	1	5
		M	1	0	0
CARNE, IND.	Meat	F	14	10	59
		M	12	4	3
CHAROLESA	Meat	F	1	1	4
		M	1	1	2

CRUZADO ABERDEEN-ANGUS	Meat	M	10	2	0
		F	10	5	7
CRUZADO ALENTEJANO	Meat	F	0	0	1
CRUZADO BBB	Meat	F	0	0	1
CRUZADO CHAROLÊS	Meat	F	7	4	59
		M	6	2	1
CRUZADO DE BLONDE	Milk	F	2	1	3
		M	2	0	0
CRUZADO DE CARNE	Meat	F	221	113	541
		M	193	53	21
CRUZADO DE LEITE	Milk	F	2	1	3
		M	1	0	0
CRUZADO FRÍSIA	Milk	M	1	0	0
		F	2	3	7
CRUZADO LIMOUSINE	Other uses	M	33	10	6
		F	40	22	174
FRISIA	Milk	F	6	7	20
GARVONESA	Meat	F	1	0	2
		M	1	0	0
LEITE, IND.	Milk	F	2	3	12
		M	1	0	0
LIMOUSINE	Other uses	F	4	3	21
		M	4	3	10
MARONESA	Meat	F	0	0	1
MERTOLENGA	Meat	F	8	6	78
		M	7	2	2
MIRANDESA	Meat	F	1	0	3
OUTRAS	Milk	F	0	0	1
PRETA	Meat	F	2	1	12
		M	2	0	0
SALERS	Milk	F	1	1	5
TIPO FRISIA	Milk	F	16	14	40
		M	16	2	1

According the previous assumptions, the following distribution can be found:

- Milk use: 112 heads
- Meat: 1506 heads
- Breeding and growing: 567 heads

In order to evaluate the economic impact in the ecosystem, the most appropriate scenario would be (in order to develop a similar analysis to the previous one for crops) obtaining the cost of each use for bovine exploitations. Unfortunately, the government of Portugal in 2011 provided the last official and public information partially related to this assessment. In order to obtain a qualitative assessment, two different official Spanish statistics were used: the technical-economical results report for milk production in bovine farms for Andalucía, Asturias, Cantabria, Castilla y León, Galicia, Navarra y País Vasco for 2015, and the State Official Newsletter where unitary value for each use (milk and meat) was set for cattle exploitation insurance purposes [27] [28].

As a methodology to calculate the economical incomes for bovine exploitation facilities, the only categories considered were milk and meat. For breeding, growing and other uses, only costs but no incomes were considered in order to calculate the overall economic impact.

According to the previous report, the average incomes and costs for an average milk cow in Spain are 3,980€/year and 3,490€ respectively for an annual production of 9,060 l/cow. For milking purposes, the annual profits in the area (according to the assumptions considered) are 54,880€ and the overall annual economic impact (profits + costs) 445,760€.

According to the Spanish Official Newsletter for meat purposes, the annual net profits and costs for each head it should be around 331€/head and 370€/head respectively. According to this numbers, the annual profits in the area are 498,486€ and the overall annual economic impact (profits + costs) 1,055,706€

There is no data for breeding, growing or another uses. In order to quantify the costs the same economical requirements than meat uses were considered. In this way, the annual profits are considered to be zero and the overall annual economic impact (profits + costs) are 209,790€

When all the categories are considered the annual profits for the **bovine exploitation** farms in the area as an ecosystem provisioning service has an **impact from an economic point** of view around **553,366€/year**. At the same, time the **overall annual economic impact** for 2017 was **1,711,256€**.

Caprine and Ovine:

According to the database of livestock management in the area of Alentejo, the ovine and caprine livestock can be classified according to five categories (weight fattening purpose based and male and female reproductive purposes based). By following data for 2011 to 2015 are presented in Table 21.

Table 21: Alentejo caprine and ovine heads livestock for 2011 to 2015.

		2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Ovine	Female >6months not covered	34,293	39,041	47,957	35,477	25,039
	Female covered 1st time	35,203	33,811	42,280	50,268	75,036
	Female	801,975	779,600	778,385	810,123	809,409

	covered 2nd or additional times					
	Male for reproduction	31,898	31,771	32,923	34,711	35,306
	Others (growing)	217,526	246,122	271,603	276,297	281,767
Caprine	Female >6months not covered	5,233	5,114	6,531	4,718	3,161
	Female covered 1st times	6,296	6,154	5,469	6,349	8,042
	Female covered 2nd or additional times	77,409	77,181	73,965	75,387	72,257
	Male for reproduction	4,261	4,481	4,353	4,388	4,343
	Others (growing)	11,722	12,305	14,197	15,270	14,984

According to conversations with EDIA, there are no ovine and caprine farms in the area under study.

4.3.3 Water consumption

Regarding the water usage, three different uses are found in this ecosystem: water use for irrigation, water use for animal farms and water use for human purposes (residential uses).

According to EDIA company, all the water used in the area under study is obtained from Alqueva Dam and then transferred to the surface water reservoirs, so no ground water bodies are officially used in the area.

Regarding the water for irrigation uses, it has been obtained approximately by area and kind of crop, being the overall consumption close to **27,100,000 m³/year** with an economic conversion, due to this provisioning service close to **29.900.000 €/year**.

Regarding the water use for animal farms, literature values were used in order to evaluate the amount of water consumed. According to [29] [30] as an average consumption, for milk production a cow uses to drink around 3 l/kg milk of water plus 4l/kg dry food. For breeding and meat production, the water consumption is only related to the amount of dry food ingested, 5.5l/kg. According to these publications, the average dry food consumed by a cow can be estimated around 11kg/day.

Based on this data, the amount of **water** in Monte Novo **dedicated to livestock**, in a **qualitative** manner, could be set at **50,620 m³/year**. This provisioning service represent an economic impact of **1,711,256€**.

Finally, the human use of surface water can be categorized according the urban cycle of water: water supply, water depuration and waste management.

The only one urban settle located in the Alqueva's demo is the village São Manços. This is a small village located in the area 2 of the demo (110 km²).

Figure 23: São Manços village [31] [32].

Due to the lack of official census for this village (the last official information (2011) set the population in 938 inhabitants), a statistical analysis for the population was studied from 1981 [33]. The results shown a clear lineal behaviour that indicated a decrease rate (6.2%/year). According to this rate, the estimated population considered for drinking water consumption was 881 inhabitants for 2017.

Based on the information provided by EDIA, the average consumption for drinking water in this area is approximately 164 l/person-day. According to this information, the annual water supply should be approximately **52,900 m³/year**. Regarding the wastewater depuration and management, in the village area a wastewater treatment plant can be found. According to the information provided by the Spanish company that built it, Ecodepur, the **annual water rate to be treated** is closer to **67,500 m³/year**.

A similar analysis to the irrigation water can be developed in order to convert this provisioning ecosystem service into economical terms. By means of the Evora's official municipality water prices list for 2018 [34], we can convert this water supply and wastewater treatment into economic impact for the area. For regular consumptions (small house, no commercial purposes), the **water supply price** is set to **0.40€/m³**, the **water treatment prices** is set to **0.35€/m³** and the **waste management price** is set to **0.055€/m³**.

According to this prices (+6% for taxes and without connection rates) and the water consumption estimation, we account for an economic impact for the region under study associated to drinking water close to **51,410 €/year**.

Summing up, the amount of water provided by the ecosystem considered as provisioning services could be estimated around **27,203,520 m³/year** with an annual economic impact in the area around **31,662,666 €/year**.

4.4 Economic benefits in the ecosystem after applying the WADI service

The next and final step in the analysis is to quantify the economic benefits associated to the use of WADI service. Water leaks can be on one side environmentally profitable (i.e. providing wild flora and fauna water or recharging underground repositories). On the other side, saving water-by-water leaks detection and subsequent reparation will save electricity (pumping), chemicals (when water treatment is present) and will increase water

availability (that could be useful for other purposes as additional irrigation, water transfers, etc.)

In the MonteNovo area there are no any groundwater repository to be recharged, no forests or wild flora/fauna are present or relevant, dry and high irrigation crops are present (additionally, the main crop is olive tree and vineyard, that are typically dry crops), livestock exploitations are residual and water purification stations are not present in the area. In this way, the only economic benefit associated to the identification and reparation of water leaks in the area will be a reduction in the water pumping electricity consumption.

According to the annual water consumption for the overall MonteNovo area, the annual pumping time and the average specific pumping power (0.46 kWh/m³) provided by EDIA the water flow for each area and the electricity consumption have been estimated. This information is included in the Table 22:

Table 22: Water flow and electricity for pumping by areas. MonteNovo.

AREA	EE1	EE2	EE4A	EE4-1	EE4
Water flow m ³ /s	0.857	1.735	0.32	1.75	0.925
Annual electricity consumption kWh/yr	1,214,828	2,459,425	453,611	2,480,688	1,311,220

The overall electricity consumption associated to the water provisioning in the area of MonteNovo (27,100,000 m³/yr) is around 7,919,773 kWh/year. It is necessary to remark that this is the water provision in the MonteNovo area. According to EDIA's record, the overall amount of water that they provided in 2018 was 263,000,000 m³ with an electrical consumption of 120,337,627 kWh. So, MonteNovo area corresponds to a 10% of the potential water managed by EDIA.

In order to calculate the economic and environmental impact benefits associated to WADI service, the CO₂ emissions associated to electricity production (based on the Portugal's electric production mix in 2018, 400 grCO₂eq/kWh [35]), the economic price for the electricity (0.0996€/kWh or 0.1835€/kwh based on industrial price without/with taxes in Portugal in 2018 [21]), and the conversion into average emissions per capita (4.54 TonCO₂eq/cap [36]), and the average emissions for a Diesel car (10,000 km/yr, 104.6 gCO₂eq/km [37]) are included in the following Table 23, assuming that a 5% of the circulating water is saved by means of WADI service:

Table 23: Economic and environmental impact of applying WADI service in MonteNovo and EDIA's facilities.

Area		Electricity reduction [kWh/yr]	Cost reduction without / with taxes [€/yr]	CO ₂ reduction [TonCO ₂ eq/yr]	Equivalent persons reduction [Person _{eq} /yr]	Equivalent cars reduction [car _{eq} /yr]
MonteNovo	EE1	60,741	6,049 / 11,146	24.3	5	23
	EE2	122,971	12,248 / 22,565	49.2	11	47
	EE4-A	22,680	2,259 / 4,162	9.1	2	9

	EE4-1	124,034	12,354 / 22,760	49.6	11	46
	EE4	65,561	6,530 / 12,030	26.2	6	25
TOTAL EDIA		6,016,881	599,281 / 1,104,098	2,406.8	530	2,300

Finally, and according to EDIA's suggestions, an additional economic benefit will be associated to the higher amount of water that could be provided to end-users along their overall facilities is water leaks are found and repaired. In case a 5% (assumed as before based on the DLV 9.1 assumptions) is applied to MonteNovo area and to EDIA's facilities the additional amount of water to be sold will be 1,355,000 and 13,150,000 m³/year. According to EDIA's information an amount close to 0.04€/m³ could be obtained for this water that will correspond to an increase in their incomes close to 54,200 €/year (MonteNovo) and 526,000 €/year (overall EDIA's facilities).

5 Conclusions

The assessment performed in both areas has highlighted the high complexity to find the required information for evaluating the water provisioning services. Regulation and cultural services were not considered due to the non-clear relation between them and the economic benefits.

Several assumptions and crossed literature data have been used when information gaps were identified so quantitative results should be considered as qualitatively quantitative.

One of the main issues identified to the WADI service impact on the benefits is the lack of a probability of detection ratio and the amount of water leaked in these leaks when they are detected and potentially repaired. Data obtained by means of WP6 flights maybe could provide this probability of detection ratio and the 5% assumed of water leaked in the area should be reformulated according to the new value that will change the scenario after the WADI application, but the initial status will be also valid.

6 References

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7 Annexes

7.1 Correspondences between CICES v4.3 classes the typologies of the MA and TEEB

Table 24: Correspondences between CICES v4.3 Classes the typologies of the MA and TEEB [38].

	CICES v4.3 Class	MA	TEEB	
Provisioning	Cultivated crops	Food	Food	
	Reared animals and their outputs			
	Wild plants, algae and their outputs			
	Wild animals and their outputs			
	Plants and algae from in-situ aquaculture			
	Animals from in-situ aquaculture			
	Surface water for drinking	Water	Water	
	Ground water for drinking			
	Fibres and other materials from plants, algae and animals for direct use or processing	Fibre, Timber, Ornamental, Biochemical	Raw materials, medicinal resources	
	Materials from plants, algae and animals for agricultural use			
	Genetic materials from all biota	Genetic materials	Genetic materials	
	Surface water for non-drinking purposes	Water	Water	
	Ground water for non-drinking purposes			
	Plant-based energy sources	Fibre	Fuels and fibres	
Animal-based energy sources				
Animal-based (mechanical) energy				
Regulation	Bio-remediation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals	Water purification and water treatment, air quality regulation	Waste treatment (water purification), air quality regulation	
	Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants, and animals			
	Filtration/sequestration/storage/accumulation by ecosystems			
	Dilution by atmosphere, freshwater and marine ecosystems			
	Mediation of smell/noise/visual impacts	Erosion regulation	Erosion prevention	
	Mass stabilisation and control of erosion rates			
	Buffering and attenuation of mass flows			
	Hydrological cycle and water flow maintenance	Water regulation	Regulation of water flows, regulation of extreme events	
	Flood protection	Natural hazard regulation		
	Storm protection			
	Ventilation and transpiration	Air quality regulation	Air quality regulation	
	Pollination and seed dispersal	Pollination	Pollination	
	Maintaining nursery populations and habitats	Pest regulation	Biological control	
	Pest control			
	Disease control	Disease regulation		
	Weathering processes	Soil formation (supporting ES)	Maintenance of soil fertility	
	Decomposition and fixing processes			
	Chemical condition of freshwaters	Water regulation	Water	
	Chemical condition of salt waters			
	Global climate regulation by reduction of greenhouse gas concentrations	Atmospheric regulation	Climate regulation	
	Micro and regional climate regulation	Air quality regulation	Air quality regulation	
	Cultural	Experiential use of plants, animals and land-/seascapes in different environmental settings	Recreation and ecotourism	Recreation and tourism
		Physical use of land-/seascapes in different environmental settings		
Scientific		Knowledge systems and educational values, cultural diversity, aesthetic values	Inspiration for culture, art and design, aesthetic information	
Educational				
Heritage, cultural				
Entertainment				
Aesthetic				
Symbolic		Spiritual and religious Values	Information and cognitive development	
Sacred and/or religious				
Existence				
Bequest				

7.2 Indicators for provisioning, regulating and cultural services for each kind of ecosystem.

Table 25: Indicators for provisioning services delivered by forests

Division	Group	Class	Indicator	
Nutrition	Biomass	Cultivated crops	Not defined	
		Reared animals and their outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meat production (e.g. Iberian pigs) Meat consumption Number of individuals 	
		Wild plants, algae and their outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distribution of heathlands and other habitats for bees Distribution of plants important for honey production Distribution of wild berries, fruits, mushrooms Distribution of wild berries Hone production/consumption Wild berries, fruits and mushroom harvest 	
		Wild animals and their outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amount of meat (hunting) Value of game Hunting records 	
		Plants and algae form in-situ aquaculture	Not defined	
		Animals form in-situ aquaculture	Not defined	
	Water	Surface water for drinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total supply of water per forest area Area of forest dedicated to preserve the water resource River discharge Reservoir water Population and per capita water consumption 	
			Ground water for drinking	Not defined
	Materials	Biomass	Fibres and other materials from plants, algae and animals for direct use or processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forest biomass stock Forest biomass increment Forest for timber, pulp wood, etc. production Commercial forest tree volume & harvesting rates Tress (e.g. cork oak for cork & pines for resins) Wood consumption (e.g. industrial roundwood. Fuelwood)
			Materials from plants, algae and animals for agricultural use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distribution of foraging areas in forest Marketed forage
Genetic materials from all biota			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distribution of plants species with biochemical/pharmaceutical uses Raw materials for medicines 	
Water		Surface water for non-drinking purposes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Same as for drinking purposes 	
		Ground water for non-drinking purposes		
Energy	Biomass-based energy sources	Plant-based resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wood fuel stock (fraction of forest biomass stock) Wood fuel production (fraction of forest biomass increment) Distribution of tress for wood production Fuel wood consumption 	
		Animal-based resources	Not defined	
	Mechanical energy	Animal-based resources	Not defined	

Table 26: Indicators for regulating services delivered by forests

Division	Group	Class	Indicator
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Mediation of waste, toxics and other nuisances	Mediation by biota	Bio-remediation by micro-organisms, algae, plants and animals	Not defined
		Filtration, sequestration, storage, accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants and animals	Not defined
	Mediation by ecosystems	Filtration, sequestration, storage, accumulation by ecosystems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Area of forest Sulphur (S) and Nitrogen (N) retention and removal
		Dilution by atmosphere, freshwater and marine ecosystems	Not defined
		Mediation of noise, smell and visual impacts	Not defined
Mediation of flows	Mass flows	Mass stabilization and control of erosion rates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Erosion protection Area of forest designated to prevention of soil erosion Area eroded by wind and water Forest cover in high slope areas Sediments removed from dams, lakes and rivers
		Buffering and attenuation of mass flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forest area designated for attenuation of mass flows Erosion risk mitigation Flood risk mitigation
	Liquid flows	Hydrological cycle and water flow maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forest area designated to preserve water resources Number of floods Water retention in forest Snow cover Infiltration Capacity for maintaining baseline flow Water storage and delivery capacity of the soil Water supply and discharge Important areas for water infiltration and headwater surroundings covered by forest Drought and water scarcity
		Flood protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Special protection areas for preventing mass flows linked to the River Basin Management Plans Reforestation of forest territories against floods Number of floods
		Gaseous/air flows	Storm protection
	Ventilation and transpiration		Not defined
	Maintenance of physical, chemical, biological conditions	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Pollination and seed dispersal
Maintaining nursery populations and habitats			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tree species distribution Conservation investments Protected Areas for nursery populations Forest area designated for habitat-landscape protection
Pest and disease control		Pest control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Host-species abundance Surface of healthy Forest Number of pests and diseases Surface affected by pest and diseases Number of IAS Damage cost
		Disease control	Not defined
Soil formation and composition		Weathering processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Area of forest Restoration costs Forest soil condition: chemical soil properties
		Decomposition and fixing processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil organic mater Amount of dead wood

	Water conditions	Chemical condition of freshwaters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thickness of the organic layer Water quality Forest area designated to preserve water resources Cost of water purification
		Chemical condition of salt waters	Not defined
	Atmospheric composition and climate regulation	Global climate regulation by reduction of greenhouse gas concentrations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon storage in forest Carbon sequestration by forest Forest growth Number of CO₂ emissions permits
		Micro and regional climate regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Albedo maps Foliar surface index Ozone and particle pollution

Table 27: Cultural services delivered by forest ecosystems

Division	Group	Class	Indicator
Physical and intellectual interactions with biota, ecosystems and land/seascapes	Physical and experiential interactions	Experiential use of plants, animals and land/seascapes in different environmental settings and physical use of land/seascapes in different environmental settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distribution of wildlife and emblematic species associated with forest Important bird areas associated with forest Area of forest accessible for recreation Number of visitors Number of hunters Ecotourism operators Area of forest accessible for hunting
	Intellectual and representative interactions	Scientific, educational, heritage, cultural, entertainment and aesthetic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citations, distribution of research project, educational projects, number of historic records Number/value of publications sold
Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with biota, ecosystems and land/seascapes	Spiritual and/or emblematic	Symbolic and sacred and/or religious	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distribution of sites of emblematic plants/forests Number of sites with recognised cultural and spiritual value Number of visitors
	Other cultural outputs	Existence and bequest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distribution of important areas for forest biodiversity and their conservation status Condition of forest-associated priority species on habitat and birds directives Distribution of sites with forest designated as having cultural values

Table 28: Indicators for provisioning services delivered by agro-ecosystems

Division	Group	Class	Cropland	Grassland
Nutrition	Biomass	Cultivated crops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yields of food and feed crops (ton/ha, ton dry matter/ha, MJ/ha) Food and feed crop area (ha) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yields (ton/ha, ton dry matter/ha, MJ/ha) Grassland area (ha)
		Reared animals and their outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Livestock data (LU/ha, Ton/yr/region) 	
		Wild plant, algae and their outputs	Not defined	
		Wild animals and their outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wild game bag data Wild game population estimates 	
		Plants and algae from in-situ aquaculture	Not defined	
		Animals from in-situ aquaculture	Not defined	
	Water	Surface water for drinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High Nature Value farmland 	
		Ground water for drinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Areas important for groundwater abstraction in agro ecosystems 	
Materials	Biomass	Fibres and other materials from plants, algae and animals for direct use or processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yields of fibre crops (ton/ha, ton dry matter/ha, MJ/ha) Fibre crop area (ha) 	Not defined
		Materials from plants, algae and		

		animals for agricultural use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manure /ton/yr) 	
		Genetic materials from all biota	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yields of crops used for medicinal and cosmetic purposes (ton/ha, yon dry matter/ha, MJ/ha) • Area of crops used for medicinal and cosmetic purposes (ha) 	
	Water	Surface water for non-drinking purposes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See freshwater ecosystems 	
		Ground water for non-drinking purposes		
Energy	Biomass-based energy sources	Plant-based resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yields of energy crops (ton/ha, yon dry matter/ha, MJ/ha) • Energy crop area (ha) • Biofuel, biodiesel bioethanol (kToe) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yields of grasslands for energy production (ton/ha, yon dry matter/ha, MJ/ha) • Grassland for energy area (ha)
		Animal-based resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy from manure treatment systems 	
	Mechanical energy	Animal-based energy	Not defined	

Table 29: Indicators for regulation and maintenance services delivered by agro-ecosystems

Division	Group	Class	Cropland	Grassland
Mediation of waste, toxics and other nuisances	Mediation by biota	Bio-remediation by micro-organisms, algae, plants and animals	Not defined	
		Filtration, sequestration, storage, accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants and animals		
	Mediation by ecosystems	Filtration, sequestration, storage, accumulation by ecosystems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concentration of pollutants in soil in agricultural areas Concentration of nutrients elements (C, N, P, K, Ca, Mg, S) in soil in agricultural areas 	
		Dilution by atmosphere, freshwater and marine ecosystems		Not defined
		Mediation of smell, noise and visual impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hedgerow length 	
Mediation of flows	Mass flows	Mass stabilization and control of erosion rates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage of soil cover in cropland (conservation tillage, zero tillage, winter crops, cover crop or intermediate crop and plant residues) Density of hedgerows Soil erosion risk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage of grassland cover Soil erosion risk
		Buffering and attenuation of mass flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of hedgerows 	Not defined
	Liquid flows	Hydrological cycle and water flow maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Retention capacity of water in agricultural soils 	
		Flood protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share of agroforestry within floodplains 	
	Gaseous /air flows	Storm protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of hedgerows 	Not defined
		Ventilation and transpiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amount of biomass 	
	Maintenance of physical, chemical, biological conditions	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Pollination and seed dispersal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pollination potential Pollinators species richness and distribution Number of beehives Areal coverage of vegetation features supporting pollination
Maintaining nursery populations and habitats			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share of High Nature Value farmland Traditional orchards 	
Pest and disease control		Pest control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of hedgerows 	
		Disease control		
Soil formation and composition		Weathering processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share of organic farming Soil organic matter content Ph of topsoil Cation exchange capacity 	
		Decomposition and fixing processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Area of N fixing crops Gross nitrogen balance 	
		Chemical condition of	Not defined	

	Atmospheric composition and climate regulation	freshwaters		
		Chemical condition of salt waters		
		Global climate regulation by reduction of greenhouse gas concentrations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon sequestered by permanent crops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon sequestered by grasslands
		Micro and regional climate regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Humidity index 	

Table 30: Indicators for cultural services delivered by agro-ecosystems

Division	Group	Class	Cropland	Grassland
Physical and intellectual interactions with biota, ecosystems and land/seascapes	Physical and experiential interactions	Experiential use of plants, animals and land/seascapes in different environmental settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors in agricultural areas Number of rural enterprises offering tourism-related services Farm tourism Walking and biking trails Number of hunting licenses, number of birdwatchers Expenditures related to hunting 	
		Physical use of land/seascapes in different environmental settings		
	Intellectual and representative interactions	Scientific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amount of scientific studies on agro-ecosystems 	
		Educational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of didactic farms 	
		Entertainment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contests and competitions related to agriculture 	
		Heritage, cultural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of agricultural-livestock fairs Number of monuments in agricultural areas Number of certified products that required traditional landscape management 	
	Aesthetic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors in agricultural areas Number of nature/agricultural landscape photos uploaded on web portals 		
Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with biota, ecosystems and land/seascapes	Spiritual and/or emblematic	Symbolic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remarkable trees Symbolic species 	
		Sacred and/or religious	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Religious monuments, pilgrim paths in agro-ecosystems 	
	Other cultural outputs	Existence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cropland or grassland in protected agricultural areas Willingness to pay for landscape measures in cropland or grassland areas 	
		Bequest		

Table 31: Indicators for ecosystem provisioning services delivered by freshwater ecosystems

Division	Group	Class	Lakes	Rivers	Ground water	Wetlands	
Nutrition	Biomass	Cultivated crops	Not defined				
		Reared animals and their outputs	Not defined				
		Wild plants, algae and their outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wild plants used in gastronomy, cosmetic, pharmaceutical uses 		Not defined	See lakes and rivers	
		Wild animals and their outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fish production Number of fisherman and hunters of waterfowls Status of fish population (species composition, biomass kg/ha) 		Not defined	See lakes and rivers	
		Plants and algae from in-situ aquaculture	Not defined				
		Animals from in-situ aquaculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Freshwater aquaculture production (e.g. sturgeon and caviar production) 		Not defined		
	Water	Surface water for drinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water exploitation index (WEI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water consumption for drinking Surface water availability Water abstracted 		Not defined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nitrate-vulnerable zones
		Ground water for drinking		Not defined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ground water bodies Ground water abstraction 	Not defined	
	Materials	Biomass	Fibres and other materials from plants, algae and animals for direct use or processing	Not defined			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wood produced (tons or volume) by riparian forest Surface of exploited wet forests (e.g. poplars) and reeds
			Materials from plants, algae and animals for agricultural use	Not defined			
Genetic materials from all biota			Not defined				
Water		Surface water for drinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water exploitation index (WEI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water use per sector Surface water availability Water abstracted Volume of water bodies 		Not defined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surface of flood-prone areas
		Ground water for drinking		Not defined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ground water bodies Ground water abstraction 	Not defined	
Energy		Biomass-based energy sources	Plant-based resources	Not defined			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Firewood produced by riparian forests
	Animal-based resources		Not defined				

	Mechanical energy	Animal-based energy	Not defined
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Table 32: Indicators for ecosystem regulation and maintenance services delivered by freshwater ecosystems

Division	Group	Class	Lakes	Rivers	Ground water	Wetlands
Mediation of waste, toxics and other nuisances	Mediation by biota	Bio-remediation by micro-organisms, algae, plants and animals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicators on water quality (microbiological data for bathing waters, BOD5 nitrate, phosphate, oxygen and saprobiological status) Nutrients loads Trophic status Area occupied by riparian forests Waste treated Number and efficiency of treatment plants 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicators on groundwater quality (NO3, pesticide, trace metals, emerging pollutants evolution) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon storage per unit of area Potential mineralization or decomposition Ecological status Nutrient concentration Nutrient retention
		Filtration, sequestration, storage and accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants and animals				
	Mediation by ecosystems	Filtration, sequestration, storage and accumulation by ecosystems				
		Dilution by atmosphere, freshwater and marine ecosystems				
		Mediation of smell, noise and visual impacts	Not defined			
Mediation of flows	Mass flows	Mass stabilization and control of erosion rates	Not defined		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ground water level evolution 	Not defined
		Buffering and attenuation of mass flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sediment retention 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sediment retention
	Liquid flows	Hydrological cycle and water flow maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Volume of water (or snow) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hydrological flow data 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surface of wetlands
		Flood protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Holding capacity flood risk maps Conservation of river and lakes banks 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water holding capacity of soils Floodplains areas Area of wetlands located in flood risk zones Conservation status of riparian wetlands 	
	Gaseous / air flows	Storm protection	Not defined		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conservation status of wetlands Area of wetlands 	
		Ventilation and transpiration	Not defined			
physical, chemical and maintenance, habitat and gene		Pollination and seed dispersal	Not defined			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Beekeeping value of wetlands
		Maintaining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biodiversity value 		Not defined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biodiversity value

	Pest and disease control	nursery populations and habitats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ecological status and morphological status 		
		Pest control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alien species Number of introduced aquatic invertebrates Number of introduced vertebrates in rivers and riparian areas 	Not defined	See lakes and rivers
		Disease control	Not defined		
	Soil formation and composition	Weathering processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fluvisols surface 	Not defined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hydromorphic soils Surface of floodplains
		Decomposition and fixing processes	Not defined		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential mineralization, decomposition, etc.
	Water conditions	Chemical condition of freshwaters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical status Ecological status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicators of ground water quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical status Ecological status Potential of water purification of wetlands
		Chemical condition of salt waters	Not defined		Not defined
	Atmospheric composition and climate regulation	Global climate regulation by reduction of greenhouse gas concentrations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C sequestration (Carbon sequestration in living biomass of riparian forest, carbon sequestered by plantations of Populus, organic carbon stored in fluvisols) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C sequestration (evolution of annual volumes of CO₂ injected, number of sires for CO₂ deep injections) 	See rivers and lakes
		Micro and regional climate regulation	Not defined		

Table 33: Indicators for ecosystem cultural services delivered by freshwater ecosystems

Division	Group	Class	Lakes	Rivers	Ground water	Wetlands
Physical and intellectual interactions with biota, ecosystems and land/seascapes	Physical and experiential interactions	Experiential use of plants, animals and land/seascapes in different environmental settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors National Parks and Natura 2000 sites Known bird watching sites 		Not defined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors Known bird watching sites Waterfowl Tourism revenue
		Physical use of land/seascapes in different environmental settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors Bathing areas and number of beaches Fishing reserves Fish abundance Fish monetary value from angling Number of fishing licenses Quality of fresh waters for fishing 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors (to thermal, mineral and mud springs and beaches, to natural reserve areas or to speleology sites) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors (waterfowl hunters and fishermen) Number of fishing licenses

	Intellectual and representative interactions	Scientific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring sites by scientists Number of scientific projects, articles and studies Classified sites (world heritage, label European tourism, etc.) 		
		Educational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors Natural Parks and Natura 2000 sites 		
		Heritage and cultural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors Natural heritage and cultural sites Number of annual cultural activities organised 		
		Entertainment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors Surface or number of wetlands located next to a bike path 		
		Aesthetic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors Contrasting landscapes Proximity to urban areas of scenic rivers or lakes 		
Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with biota, ecosystems and land/seascapes	Spiritual and/or emblematic	Symbolic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National species or habitat types 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors (to places where springs and streams with ground water origin made them historic and religious sites) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National species or habitat types
		Sacred and/or religious	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sacred/religious sites (catastrophic events or religious places) 	Not defined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sacred/religious sites (catastrophic events or religious places)
	Other cultural outputs	Existence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors Number of fishing licenses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of visitors 	See rivers and lakes
		Bequest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of association registered on animals, plants, environment, naturism 	Not defined	See rivers and lakes

Table 34: Indicators for ecosystem services delivered by marine ecosystems

Division	Group	Class	Marine inlets and transitional waters	Coastal waters	Shelf waters	Open Ocean
Nutrition	Biomass	Cultivated crops	Not defined			
		Reared animals and their outputs	Not defined			
		Wild plants, algae and their outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Harvest (ton/yr) 	Not defined		
		Wild animals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Landings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Landings (ton) 		

		and their outputs	(ton)	• CPUE (ton)		
		Plants and algae from in-situ aquaculture	• Harvest (ton/yr)		Not defined	
	Animals from in-situ aquaculture	• Harvest (ton/yr)		Not defined		
	Water	Surface water for drinking	Not defined			
Materials	Biomass	Fibres and other materials from plants, algae and animals for direct use of processing	• Harvest (ton)	• Landings (ton)	• Harvest (ton/yr)	
		Materials from plants, algae and animals for agricultural uses				
	Genetic materials from all biota	• Patents (number)	• Published articles (number)			
	Water	Surface water for non-drinking purposes	Not defined			
Energy	Biomass-based energy sources	Plant-based resources	Not defined			
		Animal-based resources				
	Mechanical energy	Animal-based energy				
Mediation of waste, toxics and other nuisances	Mediation by biota	Bio-remediation by micro-organisms, algae, plants and animals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrient load to coastal (ton/yr) • HM and POP deposition (ton/yr) • Oxyrisk 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HM and POP deposition (ton/yr) • Oxyrisk
		Filtration, sequestration, storage and accumulation by micro-organisms, algae, plants and animals				
	Mediation by ecosystems	Filtration, sequestration, storage and accumulation by ecosystems				
		Dilution by atmosphere, freshwater and marine ecosystems				
		Mediation of smell, noise and visual impacts	Not defined			
Mediation of flows	Mass flows	Mass stabilization and control of erosion rates	• Composite indices based on extent of selected emerged, submerged and	Not defined		
		Buffering and				

		attenuation of mass flows	intertidal habitats, coastline slope and coastal geomorphology, wave regime, tidal range, relative sea level and storm surge		
	Liquid flows	Hydrological cycle and water flow maintenance	Not defined		
		Flood protection	See buffering and attenuation of mass flows	Not defined	
	Gaseous / air flows	Storm protection	Not defined		
Ventilation and transpiration					
Maintenance of physical, chemical and biological conditions	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Pollination and seed dispersal	Not defined		
		Maintaining nursery populations and habitats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Submerged and intertidal habitats diversity (number) Oxygen concentration (%) Turbidity (%) Species distribution (km²/ha) Abundance and richness at age (ton/yr) Extent of marine protected areas (km²/ha) Nursery areas (km²/ha) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oxygen concentration (%) Turbidity (%) Species distribution (km²/ha) Abundance and richness at age (ton/yr) Extent of marine protected areas (km²/ha) Nursery areas (km²/ha) 	Not defined
	Pest and disease control	Pest control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presence (number) and distribution of alien species (km²) 		
		Disease control	Not defined		
	Soil formation and composition	Weathering processes	Not defined		
		Decomposition and fixing processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nitrogen removal (%) Water residence time (months) Depth/water residence time (m/yr) 	Not defined	
	Water conditions	Chemical condition of freshwaters	Not defined		
		Chemical condition of salt waters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nutrient load to coast (ton/yr) HM and POP loading (ton/yr) Oxyrisk 		
	Atmospheric composition and climate regulation	Global climate relation by reduction of GHG concentrations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C stock (ton), C sequestration (ton/yr), pH, blue C (ton) and PP (ton/yr) 		
		Micro and regional climate regulation	Not defined		
	Actual interactions with biota, ecosystems and land	Experiential use of plants, animals and land/seascapes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extent of marine protected areas (km²/ha) Presence of iconic/endangered species (number) In-water activities occurrence (number) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extent of marine protected areas (km²/ha) 	

D7.3. Report on the economic benefits for WADI demonstration sites ecosystems.

		in different environment settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recreation trips (number/yr) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presence of iconic/endangered species (number)
		Physical use of land/seascapes in different environmental settings		
	and representative interactions	Scientific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific studies (number), Documentaries, educational publications (number), visits to scientific and artistic visits exhibits (number) 	
		Educational		
		Heritage, cultural	Not defined	
		Entertainment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentaries, educational publications (number), visits to scientific and artistic visits exhibits (number) 	
Aesthetic				
Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with biota, ecosystems and land/seascapes	Spiritual and/or emblematic	Symbolic	Not defined	
		Sacred and/or religious		
	Other cultural outputs	Existence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extent of marine protected areas (km²/ha) Presence of iconic/endangered species (number) 	
Bequest				

7.3 Literature information extracted for irrigation water use evaluation

7.3.1 Assumptions

- Sunflower share uses is assumed as 70% for human uses, 25% for animal uses and 5% for energy uses [39].
- Corn share uses is assumed as 3% for human uses and 97% for animal uses [40].
- Wheat share uses is assumed as 85% for human uses and 15% for animal uses [39].
- Oats share uses is assumed as 15% for human uses and 85% for animal uses [41].
- Grape is used for making wine.
- Oats, barley and wheat produce grain and straw.

7.3.2 EDIA report information

Table 35: EDIA report agricultural information [24].

Kind of Crop	Use	Crop	Water Consumption m ³ /ha	Avg. Yield Ton/ha	Production cost €/ha	Unit cost €/kg	market value €/kg	Brute Incomes €/ha
Cereals	Human and animals feed	Corn	7,000	14	2,200 – 2,300	0.157 – 0.164	0.16 – 0.17	2,240 – 2,380
	Human and animals feed	Oats	2,500	4	550-650	0.135 – 0.162	0.15 – 0.16 grain 0.05 straw	600 - 640 grain 100 straw
	Human and animals feed	Barley	2,500	4 - 5	550 - 650	0.125 – 0.145	0.16 – 0.20 grain 0.05 straw	720 - 900 grain 112 straw
	Human and animals feed	Wheat and triticale	3,200	4 - 5	550 - 650	0.12 – 0.14	0.16 – 0.18	720 - 810 grain 112 straw
	Human feed	Rice	11,000	4 - 5	1,900 – 2,100	0.41	0.28 – 0.30	1,500
Protein product	Human feed	Pea	2,200 – 2,500	6 – 6.5	1,120 – 1,200	0.179 – 0.192	0.22 – 0.25	1,375 – 1,563
	Human feed	Chickpea	2,500	1.2 - 2	615 - 640	0.35 – 0.37	0.565	848 – 1,130
	Animals feed	Lupin bean	2,500	1 - 2	400 - 500	0.27 – 0.33	0.45 – 0.5	675 - 750
Grass and forage	Animal feed	Ray grass	8,000	10 - 12	980 – 1,290	0.1 – 0.13	0.10 – 0.15	1,100 – 1,650
	Animals feed	Alfalfa	7,000	12 - 17	2,150 – 2,300 1st year 1,700 – 1,800 2nd and next years	0.1 – 0.19	0.15 – 0.17	2,250 – 2,550
	Animal feed	Sorghum	8,000	22 - 24	1,500 – 1,600	0.06 – 0.07	0.07 – 0.1	1,610 – 2,300
Oleaginous	Human and animal feed and biodiesel	Sunflower	2,500 – 4,500	2.5 - 4	700 - 900	0.21-0.27	0.35 – 0.40	1,137 – 1,300
	Biodiesel	Colza	1,500	2 - 3	700 - 800	0.28 – 0.32	0.37 – 0.42	925 – 1,050
Opium	Medical uses	Opium poppy	2,500 - 3500	1.5 - 2	1,100 – 1,300	Private contracts		
Fruit tree	Human feed	Apricot	6,000	4 - 7	14,000 – 18,000 start-up, 5,000 – 6,000 exploitation	0.90 – 1.1	1.44	5,760 – 10,800
	Human feed	Plum	6,000	15 - 25	14,500 – 17,000 start-up 4,500 – 6,000 exploitation	0.22 – 0.30	0.77	11,550 – 19,250
	Human feed	Citrus	4,500 – 7,000	15 - 20	12,000 – 18,000 start-up 5,000 – 6,000 exploitation	0.29 – 0.34	0.52	7,800 – 10,400
	Human feed	Apple	7,000 – 8,000	16 - 20	12,000 – 18,000 start-up 5,000 – 6,000 exploitation	0.28 – 0.33	0.65	10,400 – 13,000
	Human feed	Peach/ Nectarine	6,000 – 7,000	12 - 15	15,000 – 18,000 start-up 6,000 – 7,000 exploitation	0.44 – 0.52	0.64	8,000 – 9,600
	Human feed	Pear	7,000 – 8,000	20 - 30	17,000 – 19,000 start-up 7,000 – 8,000	0.28 – 0.32	0.75	15,000 – 22,500

D7.3. Report on the economic benefits for WADI demonstration sites ecosystems.

					exploitation			
	Human feed	Pomegranate	6,000 – 7,000	10 - 15	7,900 – 8,300 start-up 1,800 – 2,200 exploitation	0.1 – 0.125	1.6	16,000 – 24,000
	Human feed	Olive tree	2,500 – 3,500	9 - 10	3,650 – 4,250 start-up 900 – 1,100 exploitation	0.09 – 0.115 olive	4 – 4.5 Oil	4,620 – 4,690
	Human feed	Grape	5,000 – 6,000 table 2500 - 3000 wine	25 - 30 table 7.5 - 10 wine	16,000 – 18,000 wine 80,000 – 100,000 table start-up 2,500 – 3,000 wine exploitation	0.285 – 0.34 wine	0.30 – 0.40 Wine 1.40 – 1.95 Table	2,625 – 3,500 wine
Nuts	Human feed	Almond	3,500 – 5,000	1.5 – 2.5	4,500 – 5,500 start-up 2,500 – 3,500 exploitation	1.25 – 1.75 smashed	3 - 4 smashed	6,000 – 8,000 smashed
	Human feed	Walnut	7,500 – 8,500	2 – 4	4,000 – 5,000 start-up 3,500 – 4,000 exploitation	1.13 – 1.33	2.75 – 3.5	9,000 – 10,500
	Human feed	Hazelnut	7,500 – 8,500	3 - 4	N/A	1.7 – 1.9	N/A	5,950 – 6,650
horticultural	Human feed	Sugar beetroot	5,000 – 6,000	95	2,100 – 2,300	0.034 – 0.036	N/A	N/A
	Human feed	Pumpkin	6,000 – 7,000	30 - 40	4,500 – 5,500	0.13 – 0.16	0.2	6,300
	Human feed	Garlic	6,500 – 7,500	8 - 12	6,500 – 7,000	0.65 – 0.70	0.90 – 1.15	9,000 – 11,500
	Human feed	Potato	5,000 – 7,000	35 - 40	4,500 – 5,200	0.12 – 0.138	0.15 – 0.18	5,250 – 6,750
	Human feed	Onion	7,000 – 9,000	35 - 40	4,000 – 4,500	0.105 – 0.12	0.19	7,125
	Human feed	Cabbage / Broccoli	1,000 – 1,500	10 - 12	2,400 – 2,800	0.218 – 0.255	0.265	2,915
	Human feed	Melon / watermelon	5,000 – 6,500	20 - 35	4,500 – 5,500	0.112 – 0.137	0.20 – 0.30	8,000 – 12,000
	Human feed	Pepper	8,000 – 9,000	40 - 45	8,500 – 9,200	0.20 – 0.22	0.18 – 0.25	10,725
	Human feed	Tomato	8,000 – 10,000	90 - 100	6,000 – 7,000	0.063 – 0.073	0.08	6,460
Wild fruits	Human feed	Strawberry	7,000 – 8,000	70 - 80	350,000 – 450,000 start-up 80,000 – 85,000 exploitation	1.05 – 1.14	2.5 – 3	187,500 – 225,000
	Human feed	Blueberry	7,000 – 10,000	8 - 10	50,000 – 60,000 start-up 25,000 – 30,000 exploitation	2.75 – 3.33	3 – 4	27,000 – 36,000

7.3.3 Number of bovine heads by race and gender in Alentejo (2017).

Table 36: Number of bovine heads by race and gender in Alentejo (2017)

Race	Gender	Heads of livestock by age		
		<1 year	1-2 years	>2 years
ABERDEEN-ANGUS	F	323	214	1,148
	M	306	247	438
ALETEJANA	F	3,117	2,659	24,984
	M	2,989	1,687	394
AROUQUESA	F	0	1	16
	M	0	1	1
BARROSA	F	148	57	564
	M	131	8	24
BLANC - BLUE BELGE	F	0	1	3
	M	1	0	4
BLONDE D AQUITAINE	M	67	53	130
	F	70	84	432
BRAVA DE LIDE	M	1,949	1,869	4,227
	F	1,932	1,861	10,107
BRAVA DOS AÇORES	M	0	0	2
BÚFALO	F	0	0	1
	M	1	0	0
CACHENA	F	510	270	1,878
	M	418	27	76
CARNE, IND.	F	4,787	3,418	21,067
	M	4,101	1,535	1,064
CHAROLESA	F	242	225	1513
	M	253	235	748
CRUZADO ABERDEEN-ANGUS	M	3,596	863	87
	F	3,638	1,886	2,444
CRUZADO ALENTEJANO	F	32	16	277
	M	40	5	8
CRUZADO BBB	F	102	30	192
	M	101	30	12
CRUZADO CHAROLÊS	F	2,424	1,532	20,883
	M	2,186	754	493
CRUZADO DE BLONDE	F	624	372	1,140
	M	537	151	36
CRUZADO DE CARNE	F	78,312	40,089	191,900
	M	68,522	18,803	7,267
CRUZADO DE LEITE	F	750	446	1,133
	M	493	78	26

CRUZADO FRÍZIA	M	414	38	47
	F	839	905	2,360
CRUZADO LIMOUSINE	M	11,574	3,666	2,113
	F	14,112	7,848	61,750
CRUZADO SIMMENTAL-FLECKVIEH	F	43	26	23
	M	29	25	8
FRISIA	F	2,096	2,533	7,102
	M	9	9	59
GARVONESA	F	228	135	817
	M	195	27	32
HEREFORD	F	1	0	6
	M	1	0	0
JARMELISTA	F	0	0	2
JERSEY	M	5	1	0
	F	6	7	18
LEITE, IND.	F	576	1,205	4,104
	M	294	98	62
LIMOUSINE	F	1,474	1,203	7,560
	M	1,389	951	3,612
MARINHOA	F	9	5	49
	M	11	4	6
MARONESA	F	89	44	252
	M	84	17	16
MERTOLENGA	F	2,854	2,291	27,681
	M	2,508	624	706
MINHOTA	F	2	0	10
	M	0	0	2
MIRANDESA	M	163	12	31
	F	229	124	1,192
NORUEGUESA	M	41	0	1
	F	40	5	7
OUTRAS	F	110	44	186
	M	110	9	9
PRETA	F	593	421	4,087
	M	557	159	109
RAMO GRANDE	F	0	0	1
	M	0	6	0
SALERS	F	197	186	1,725
	M	164	65	129
SIMMENTAL-FLECKVIEH	F	0	0	10
	M	0	1	0
TIPO FRISIA	F	5737	4934	14,322